

Questionnaire: Workshop

"THE VALORISATION OF BUILT HERITAGE FOR EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: FROM THE PROJECT TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF "PERCURSO ARTE NOVA" IN THE EDUCITY APP"

The aim of this questionnaire is to collect your perception of the workshop and the Arte Nova Trail game, developed in the EduCITY app, as well as to find out your opinion and experience on topics such as built heritage, sustainability and sustainable development.

The structure of the questionnaire is organised into five main areas:

- A) Initial knowledge and conceptions about heritage, competences for sustainability and sustainable development;
- B) Perceptions of the workshop, the game and its educational dimension;
- C) Practical application of the knowledge acquired in professional contexts;
- D) Contributions, suggestions and reflections for future improvement;
- E) Profile of the participants.

The questionnaire is anonymous and the data will be processed for educational and scientific purposes only. The expected completion time is around 15/20 minutes. There are no right or wrong answers. What matters is your opinion.

Thank you for your co-operation!

A. Starting Point: Knowledge and Conceptions

This section presents the initial perceptions of the participants, the evaluation of the workshop and the *Art Nouveau Path* game, and reflections on the experience and its applicability.

A.1 Did you already know about the concept of built heritage?

Yes	No	Not sure
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

A.2 Have you ever attended a workshop/training course on the theme of built heritage?

Select another if you are not sure, but can name the name/theme of the training you attended.

Yes	No	Other
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

A.3 Were you familiar with the concept of competences for sustainability?

Select other if you are not sure, but can name the name/theme of the training undertaken.

Yes	No	Other
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

A.4 Have you attended training on competences for sustainability?

Select other if you are unsure but can name the name/theme of the training you have attended.

Yes	No	Other
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

A.5 Do you understand "Sustainability" to be the same as "Sustainable Development"?

Select other if you are unsure but can name the name/theme of the training you have attended.

Yes	No	Not sure
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

B. Reflections of the Experience: From Heritage to Sustainability

This section brings together the participants' perceptions of heritage, sustainability and the experience with the game and workshop, assessing its educational and training impact.

B.1. Tick your answer on the scale. The response scale for each statement is between: 1 - "Don't agree" and 6 - "Agree".

	Don't agree					Agree
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Heritage and Sustainability						
B.1.1 I understand the importance of built heritage in our culture.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.2 I recognise built heritage as an educational element.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.3 I understand its relationship with competences for sustainability.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.3. Built heritage can contribute to sustainable development.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.4 The workshop raised my awareness of the importance of heritage.	<input type="radio"/>					
Art Nouveau Trail" game						
B.1.5 The game establishes links with different subject areas.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.6. The game contributes to the development of critical and systemic thinking.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.7 The questions and feedback promote reflection on sustainable behaviour.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.8. The game reinforces the link between identity, memory and sustainability.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.9 Augmented Reality enriches learning and promotes meaningful engagement.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.10 The gaming experience was engaging and motivating.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.11 The game can be used in educational and tourist contexts.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.12. I realise the value of Aveiro's Art Nouveau as an educational tool.	<input type="radio"/>					
Workshop and Methodology						
B.1.13. The workshop was well structured and easy to follow.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.14. The content and materials were relevant, useful and of high quality.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.15. There were adequate opportunities for active participation.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.16. The simulation helped to understand the topics covered.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.17. The workshop met my expectations.	<input type="radio"/>					
B.1.18. I would like to take part in more workshops on similar topics.	<input type="radio"/>					

C. Transfer to Practice: Post-workshop Applications

This section analyses the practical applicability of the knowledge acquired and the potential of the game in the professional and educational context.

C.1 Can you apply the knowledge acquired in your professional context?

Yes	No
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

C.2 Do you see yourself using the game in a professional context?

Yes	No
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

C.3 Would you play the game for leisure?

Yes	No
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

C.4 Do you think the game could be used with tourists/visitors?

Yes	No
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

C.5 Do you find it easy to identify competences for sustainability in the questions in the game?

Yes	No
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

C.6 Are you familiar with GreenComp - the European Competence Framework for Sustainability?

Yes	No
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

C.7 Can you name one or more competences for sustainability?

Yes	No
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

D. Between Ideas and Possibilities: Inspirations for the Future

This section collects the participants' reflections, suggestions and perceptions of the game and workshop, offering valuable contributions for their improvement and for future training initiatives.

D.1 What do you think about Augmented Reality content? Give examples.

(explain, but you can use topics)

D.2 What did you think of the gaming experience?

(explain, but you can use topics)

D.3 What did you think of the graphic design/features?

(explain, but you can use topics)

D.4 Would you recommend this game to other teachers? Why?

(explain, but you can use topics)

D.5 What suggestions do you have for improving future workshops/trainings?

(explain, but you can use topics)

D.6 General comments on the educational potential of the game/workshop.

(explain, but you can use topics)

E. Profile

E.1 Age range

(Tick)

[20- 25[<input type="radio"/>
[26 - 30[<input type="radio"/>
[31 - 35[<input type="radio"/>
[36 - 40[<input type="radio"/>
[41 - 45[<input type="radio"/>
[46 - 50[<input type="radio"/>
[51 - 55[<input type="radio"/>
[56 - 60[<input type="radio"/>
[61 - 65[<input type="radio"/>
[66 - 70[<input type="radio"/>
over 71	<input type="radio"/>

E.2 Training (scientific area)